

PICUM

For undocumented migrants,
for social justice.

WP7 Participatory Action Research (PAR)

Migrant organisations led actions

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1. Introduction

DignityFIRM is a European project focused on promoting **dignity for migrant workers facing multiple forms of irregularity in the Farm-to-Fork sectors**. These workers are essential to agriculture, food processing, hospitality, and delivery services, yet their contributions are often met with exclusion and precarious conditions. At a time when the EU is pursuing major transitions toward sustainability and resilience, the project seeks to understand the challenges they face and the gap between policy goals and everyday realities. Through context-specific research, DignityFIRM aims to inform strategies and policy measures that uphold migrant workers' rights while supporting the wellbeing of the communities in which they live and work.

This deliverable builds on the Cross-Country comparative report, which presented the overall Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodology applied across three case studies and documented the full PAR process up to the co-design of actions with migrant workers.

Whereas the previous report focused on the analytical and comparative dimensions of the PAR process, and in particular on the insights and reflections of the focus groups, the present document provides a more detailed account of the

action phase implemented in each of the three local contexts:

Amsterdam, The Netherlands – Actions co-developed and carried out by Here to Support together with the group of migrant workers who participated in the action phase of the focus groups facilitated by Hamo Salheim, coordinated by Fanny Van der Vooren.

Seville, Spain – Actions co-developed and implemented by Mujeres Supervivientes and the group of migrant workers involved in the action phase of the focus groups. The action design phase was facilitated by Lina Marcela Rincón Barón, and the implementation phase by Roberto Cruz, both coordinated by Antonia Ávalos.

Wrocław, Poland – Actions co-developed and implemented by Nomada Association in collaboration with the Latin American Workers' Trade Union in Poland, together with the migrant workers participating in the action phase of the focus groups facilitated by Rocío Flores Torres, coordinated by Tomasz Bauer.

Individual, in-depth PAR case study reports for each country will be published in early 2026:

Participatory Action Research Case Study: Amsterdam, The Netherlands, Here to Support – Salheim, H., & Van der Vooren, F. (2026).

Participatory Action Research Case Study: Seville, Spain, Mujeres Supervivientes – Rincón Barón, L. M., & Ávalos Torres, A. (2026).

Participatory Action Research Case Study: Wrocław, Poland, NOMADA Association – Flores, R., & Bauer, T. (2026).

This deliverable includes a narrative explanation of the action plan and implementation for each of the case studies and the collection of the materials produced. The following sections include a description of the various actions taken by peer researchers and participants in the three cities chosen for the PAR approach: Amsterdam, Seville, and Wrocław.

2. Joint Action

As a preliminary joint action, the PAR coordination team decided to record a video during the second in-person PAR training workshop in Wrocław, that brought together the three teams for the case studies in Amsterdam, Seville and Wrocław, and the coordination from PICUM.

The project was invited to share the PAR insights at the IMISCOE annual conference in Paris in July 2025, but the impossibility for the peer-researchers to attend due to timeframes, restrictions of movement and excessive participation fees became a challenge. The idea that a non-migrant researcher was going to present the

benefits of PAR when working alongside with migrant peer-researchers felt particularly absurd, so the reflections of the three peer-researchers were collected and presented in Paris in the form of the video.

VIDEO:
The voices of migrant researchers: Participatory Action Research in DignityFIRM

Screenshots from the video The voices of migrant researchers

3. Actions in Amsterdam

3. a) Introduction

The focus groups highlighted that undocumented people in the Netherlands face persistent fear of deportation, which affects every aspect of daily life and severely limits access to basic services such as banking, formal employment, and legal housing. Participants reported highly precarious working conditions, usually without contracts, with irregular hours, low wages, and little ability to negotiate or speak out due to fear of replacement or detection. Work was often found through personal networks and far below participants' qualification levels. Housing insecurity was severe, with many experiencing homelessness, overpayment, or constant risk of eviction.

Limited knowledge about rights was another major issue, both among undocumented communities and among professionals, leading to situations where people were refused healthcare or faced detention when reporting crimes. Participants also described challenges related to digital payments, lack of access to banking, and workplace hierarchies that left them vulnerable to exploitation. Overall, the ongoing insecurity, lack of legal pathways, and uncertainty about the future placed a significant psychological burden on participants.

Based on these findings, participants concluded that the most needed measure in the Netherlands is the possibility to regularise through work. When imagining

the future, the common aspiration was to obtain a residence permit that would allow them to work regularly, rent housing, and build stable lives.

All actions under this project were therefore designed to contribute to steps toward a campaign for regularisation through work. It is important to note that such a campaign cannot be fully developed within the current budget and timeframe of the PICUM/DignitFIRM project, and Here to Support is exploring additional funding opportunities to continue the work beyond March.

Furthermore, several urgent issues identified in the focus groups, particularly the lack of knowledge about rights, require long-term action. These needs are addressed by Here to Support beyond the scope of this project through the organisations' broader work.

3.b) Operational objectives of the action campaign

In order to design the action phase campaign, the following issues were identified as elements to be addressed with the actions:

Lack of association between undocumented people and 'work' in Dutch media; need for media attention representing experiences and the idea of regularisation.

Being undocumented comes with constant fear of deportation; need for

lobbying for regularisation through work.

Limited association of undocumented people with ‘work’ in Dutch media; need for increased visibility of experiences and regularisation.

Need for sustained lobbying efforts involving unions, companies, and municipalities.

In order to answer these issues, the Amsterdam team designed the following set of actions:

Creation of videos and social media messaging to engage with the public.

They worked on a strategic dissemination plan with the goal of reaching 200,000 people.

Create visibility by collaborating with local media.

Collaborate with key stakeholders and partner organisations to take steps in advocacy. towards employers, the municipality of Amsterdam and, eventually, the Dutch national government.

3.c) Compilation of the actions

Stakeholder engagement: Here to Support held meetings with [FNV Migrant Domestic Workers](#) and the [Hospitality Union of the FNV](#) to discuss the development of the campaign for regularisation through work. These conversations proved fruitful, providing insight into ongoing national developments and opportunities for

collaboration, involving the NGO [Stichting LOS](#) and [Cordaan](#), the largest domestic work company in the Netherlands, which reported two-year waiting lists for its services; this connection was considered potentially significant for future collaboration. Together with the representative of the Hospitality Union, plans were made to establish a working group of organisations to initiate advocacy efforts with the municipality in support of regularisation through work.

Dissemination plan: A dissemination plan for January–March 2026 was developed in collaboration with the creative studio Hey Neighbours, outlining forthcoming actions aimed at increasing public and institutional awareness of regularisation and its implications for society. The plan envisaged a strong focus in the first quarter on generating publicity around the PAR research, ensuring that the findings became visible in the media and contributed to public debate. Cooking videos produced during the project would be shared in a targeted manner, and their content repurposed into shorter formats to enhance visibility across social media and advertisement channels.

The plan further identified the creation of a network of companies supportive of regularisation as essential for the continuation of the campaign. Companies would be approached directly with a concise information sheet and a clear call to action, enabling Here to Support to map potential allies. Includio, a subsidiary of Cordaan, emerged as a promising partner

through existing contacts with FNV Domestic Workers. Recognising that companies need multiple points of engagement to adopt a public stance, the plan emphasised regular communication via LinkedIn—the platform where employers and decision-makers are most active. A dedicated campaign account was under consideration to have clearer oversight of engagement, to build a visible network, and to monitor the growth of the movement.

Videos and social media messaging: A campaign based on cooking videos with migrants to share messages for regularisation was produced together with Studio HER. The objective was to reflect the realities and voices of undocumented people, and to create media in which the voices and statements of undocumented people are centred, contrary to stereotypical messages.

The 3 cooking videos have already been produced and are available here for reporting purposes, but will be made public via social media between January and March 2026 following the dissemination campaign designed to maximize the impact.

Screenshots from the three cooking videos for social media

[Pancit Bihon - Philippines](#) With Marion

[Jollof Rice - Nigeria](#) With Isaac

[Gima - Sudan](#) With Hamo

Best Practice video: An additional video was produced as part of the Best Practice video series for DignityFIRM including an interview to the peer researcher and to the participants of the cooking video campaign. This was published in October with the objective to raise awareness on the realities of migrants in the Netherlands before the national election that took place on October 29.

Screenshot for the Best Practice video

Local media presence: The peer-researcher conducted two interviews with local newspapers: Dwarskrant and Z-Krant (Check Annex AMST 01, printed media). He explained the project, the ideas for the action, and reflected on the findings from the focus groups. The Dwarskrant is published in the East of Amsterdam, and the Z-Krant is published throughout the city of Amsterdam.

Podcast series (forthcoming): Here to Support worked with participants from the focus groups to create a series of podcasts

that recorded statements about their experiences working in the food industry, with the aim of highlighting the human realities behind existing policies. The first episode, interviewing the coordinator of DignityFIRM Tesseltje de Lange, was recorded on December 10, 2025, and additional episodes are planned to be recorded and published between January and March 2026.

Academic dissemination: On 8 October 2025, the peer researcher and the coordinator went to Bielefeld University in Germany to present the work of Here to Support, and the findings and action plan of the project at the [INTER.SECT symposium](#): *Shifting grounds: Rethinking and navigating the uncertainty of migration trajectories, governance regimes and research.*

Peer-researcher at the INTER-SECT symposium

A similar presentation will be held online for the 1st International Conference on Movement and Integration: Migrants,

Agency, and Media by Université Ibn Zohr in Morocco, Agadir in February 2026.

4. Actions in Seville

4.a) Public event: Conference on migrant unionism

The PAR initiative in Seville unfolded in two interconnected phases. The first examined the possibilities for autonomous migrant unionism in the hospitality and catering sector, mapping life and labour conditions, everyday disputes, coping mechanisms, and expressions of migrant agency.

The second phase focused on collective action and political engagement, beginning with a public conference held on 26 September 2025 at Casa Palacio Pumarejo under the title *“Is autonomous unionism among migrant workers in the hospitality sector possible?”*.

Advertising flyer for the public event

This event brought together migrant workers, activists, community organisers, and legal experts to discuss pressing social and labour issues affecting the sector. During the conference, the case study report *Condiciones de vida y laborales de personas migrantes en el sector de la hostelería y la restauración* was presented.

The conference covered the following topics:

Mental health, gendered vulnerabilities and the importance of trust-building, by Lina Rincón, the first peer-researcher for the PAR case study;

Migrant agency and the value of humanising support structures, by Ruth Ledezma, migrant worker on hospitality sector;

Anti-racist and anticolonial activism, by Silvana Cabrera, spokesperson for the migrant-led regularisation initiative [RegularizaciónYa!](#);

Personal testimonies of labour abuse and precarity, by Roberto Cruz, second peer-researcher for the Spanish case study in charge of the action implementation;

Legal analysis regarding labour rights and structural discrimination, by Pastora Filigrana, Spanish Roma lawyer, trade unionist, feminist, columnist, and human rights activist.

Discussions covered a wide range of themes, including structural barriers to labour rights enforcement, everyday discrimination, workplace abuses, lack of

recognition, and the role of education, innovation, organisation, and alliances in defending migrant workers' rights.

4.b) Follow-up actions: Community strengthening, support and training

Following the conference, a series of support and community-building activities were implemented to respond to the needs identified by participants.

Direct advisory support was provided on documentation processes, employment contracts, housing difficulties, access to healthcare, schooling for children, and practical self-care.

Training sessions and workshops connected political participation with practices of collective care, emphasising how emotional well-being and political resistance are intertwined. Shared meals, open conversations, and spaces for mutual support were intentionally integrated to strengthen trust and solidarity.

Participants addressed challenges such as uprootedness, grief, ongoing structural violence, lack of safe or legal housing options, depression, homelessness, sudden eviction, and the emotional burden of being unable to say goodbye to deceased relatives. These gatherings created a supportive environment where participants could reflect collectively on their experiences, confront their vulnerability, and reinforce networks of care and resistance within the community.

4.c) Dignity against labour exploitation video

Advocacy work during this phase included the development of the [video](#) “*Personas Migrantes del Sector de la Hostelería, Dignidad contra explotación laboral*”. The video served as both an awareness-raising tool and a means to document the realities identified through the PAR process. It highlights the labour rights violations experienced by migrant hospitality workers while also portraying their dignity, agency, and commitment to challenging exploitation. Through visual storytelling, the video aimed to reach broader audiences, stimulate debate, and position the voices of migrant workers at the centre of public conversations about labour rights and regularisation.

Screenshot of the video “*Dignidad contra explotación laboral*”(Dignity against labour exploitation)

d) Heyzine: Digital photo exhibition

Pictures from the photographic project Heyzine

The video was complemented by a digital photographic exhibition called Heyziine

capturing the everyday experiences, struggles, resilience, and aspirations of migrant hospitality workers in Seville. The photographic project provided a visual narrative that deepened understanding of the structural pressures faced by these workers and the forms of agency they mobilise in response.

4.e) Additional materials

In addition, an informative brochure is currently being produced to raise awareness about the realities of working in the Spanish hospitality sector. This brochure is intended primarily for foreign workers considering migration to Spain, offering them grounded, accessible information about labour conditions, risks, and rights before arrival. Together, the video, exhibition, and brochure form a coherent set of advocacy tools linking research findings with public engagement and migrant-led communication. A series of stickers was also produced and shared between migrant workers in Seville (Check Annex SEVI-01).

5. Actions in Wroclaw

5.a) Introduction

The Action Phase constituted the second part of the PAR project, implemented after the diagnostic stage based on two focus groups and the Action Focus Group. Its purpose was to implement the actions proposed and agreed upon by the participants—migrant workers experiencing irregular status and labour rights violations.

These activities were structured around four core components:

- **Mapping of communities and building the Action Group;**
 - **Training and capacity building;**
 - **Advocacy and dissemination activities**
- Intercultural activities.**

Each component directly addressed the problems identified by participants in the focus group phase and aligned with the key goal of PAR: to develop actions jointly with migrants that respond to real, everyday challenges while strengthening their agency.

5.b) Mapping communities and building the Action Group (August–September 2025)

The first stage of the Action Phase focused on bringing together a committed group of participants and strengthening links with migrant communities. **Formation of the Action Group:** based on their active involvement in earlier focus groups and recommendations from peers, an action group of eight members was established, comprising six people from Colombia, one from Ukraine, and one from Türkiye. Members expressed a strong willingness to act as community leaders, disseminate information, and support collective advocacy efforts. A WhatsApp group was created to facilitate ongoing communication and coordination.

Reaching migrant communities: in parallel, members of the Action Group engaged in outreach within their personal

and professional networks. Through conversations with acquaintances and co-workers, they shared information about the project and encouraged participation in the upcoming training sessions. These exchanges also helped identify recurring problems in workplaces and living conditions, providing insights that informed subsequent stages of the project.

Distribution of informational materials:

to reinforce this outreach, printed informational leaflets were produced and distributed in locations frequently visited by migrant workers, including workplaces, community spaces, and local service points. Digital dissemination took place through social media channels commonly used within these communities. This combined approach not only increased awareness of the project but also contributed to mapping areas where migrant workers in precarious conditions are concentrated.

Check Annex WROC-01 to see the materials used for the mapping and action group consolidation.

5.c) Training sessions (September–October 2025)

Training constituted a key element of the Action Phase. Its purpose was to prepare the Action Group for further work and to provide essential knowledge to a broader group of migrant workers. The programme consisted of two main components: closed training for the Action Group and open online sessions accessible to the wider community.

Closed training for the Action Group: two in-person training sessions were conducted.

The first, “Qualitative research in practice” included interviews and documentation of labour rights violations, introduced participants to qualitative research methodology, the ethics of fieldwork, and the preparation of interview scenarios, equipping community leaders with practical tools for documenting violations.

The second training, ‘Storytelling and communication for community leaders,’ focused on interview techniques, ethical handling of sensitive personal narratives, the basics of documenting abuses, and tools for creating video materials and public narratives.

Open online training – “[Community Support Academy](#)”: these sessions were delivered in English with Spanish interpretation and attracted between 50 and 75 participants each, primarily from Latin American communities.

The programme included the following topics:

- 18 Sept, 18:00 – Tenants’ rights and protection against landlord abuse
- 24 Sept, 18:00 – Taxes and health insurance in Poland: practical basics
- 2 Oct, 18:00 – Legalisation of residence and work in Poland: practical guide
- 4 Oct, 15:00 – Labour law in Poland and protection against employer abuse

These open trainings responded directly to key issues highlighted during the focus group phase, particularly gaps in knowledge regarding labour law, tenancy rights, residence and legalisation procedures, and Poland’s tax and insurance systems.

5.d) Advocacy and dissemination activities (October–December 2025)

Creation of informational materials – mentoring and info-videos: following the training, members of the Action Group participated in mentoring sessions focused on both the content and technical aspects of video storytelling. Through these sessions, participants learned how to craft concise and engaging narratives, how to combine educational and personal elements, and the basics of video editing and organising material. One direct outcome was a short video promoting solidarity among migrant workers and encouraging unionisation, which was published on the Facebook page and communication channels of the Latin American trade union.

Screenshot of the solidarity promotion video

Documentation of labour rights violations – mentoring: the Action Group also received mentoring in preparing and conducting interviews documenting labour rights violations. With the mentor’s support, they developed interview scenarios and strategies for organising and archiving data. This stage, however, encountered several challenges, including maintaining motivation over a long project period, balancing participation with demanding workloads, and navigating the ethical and emotional difficulties of speaking with individuals who had experienced harm. As a result, the interviews were ultimately conducted by the peer-researcher and one participant from Türkiye. Mentoring continued into early December, focusing on extracting key information from interviews, identifying “red flags”, and archiving data in the project database—skills that will support future documentation efforts.

Cooperation with the media: advocacy activities also involved extensive

engagement with national and international media, through which the peer-researcher contributed multiple interviews. As a result, the issue of migrant worker exploitation—particularly concerning Latin American workers—gained increased visibility in public debate. Media outputs included:

Podcasts

25 Aug 2025 – Cuentame algo: Abusos laborales en Polonia – conversación con Vanessa Ruggiero y Rocío Flores

[LINK](#)

26 Aug 2025 – Otra TV: La migración no es como la pintan – conversación entre Carmen Ramirez Boscan y Rocío Flores

[LINK](#)

Press publications

1 Oct 2025 – Al Jazeera (A. Pikulicka-Wilczewska): In Poland, migrant workers from Latin America report abuse, exploitation

[LINK](#)

6 Nov 2025 – Polityka (A. Domasławski): Polskie piekło Kolumbijczyków (The Polish hell of Colombians)

[LINK](#)

Television

September 2025 – TVP World: Exposing forced labor: Trafficking crisis in Poland | Tomasz Bauer

[LINK](#)

Cooperation with public authorities: advocacy also extended to institutional engagement. On 12 November 2025, the peer-researcher and project coordinator

participated in a meeting with the Deputy Marshal of the Senate, Magdalena Biejat. During this discussion, the Deputy Marshal requested a list of agencies suspected of labour law violations, examined the need to ensure the safety of harmed migrant workers, and agreed on next steps, including follow-up meetings with the Ministry of Labour and the National Labour Inspectorate (PIP).

The peer-researcher Rocío Flores with Deputy Marshal of the Magdalena Biejat

A petition prepared by the Latin American Trade Union, with support from the Workers' Initiative (OZZ IP), was presented during the meeting, outlining four key demands (See Annex WROC-02 for the full petition):

- The right to regular stay for migrants who take employers to court;
- Ending the obligation of the labour inspectorate to report migrants to border authorities;
- Granting new supervisory powers to the labour inspectorate;

- Enabling regularisation for non-EU migrants living in Poland without formal status.

Deputy Marshal Biejat expressed interest in the DignityFIRM project and signalled her willingness to participate in future dissemination events.

Participation in the VI Social Women's Congress (Poznań, 3–5 October 2025)

The peer-researcher Rocío Flores at the [Social Congress of Women](#)

The peer-researcher took part in a [panel](#) on the impact of military spending on welfare systems, especially on women—including migrant women in precarious situations. The panel discussed economic crises, conflicts, inequalities, and feminist, transnational strategies of resistance. She was accompanied by four women from Turkish and Colombian communities.

5.e) Intercultural activities (October–March)

Intercultural activities planned for the period October to March were developed

to create opportunities for community building, not only within the migrant communities but with a broader population. Within this framework, two main activities were organised:

“Día de Muertos” event – 31 October: in collaboration with the network Latinas en Polonia, an event for migrant women was organised on 31 October. The gathering showcased elements of Mexican culture, created a welcoming space for social connection, and strengthened ties and solidarity among migrant women participating in the project.

Planned final event – March: a final event is planned for the end of the project. Its purpose is to bring participants together to express appreciation for their involvement, share reflections, and foster connections across different national communities. The event will also provide an opportunity to discuss the project’s activities, reinforce the visibility of migrants in the public sphere, and promote self-organisation and labour rights.

Annexes

Annex 1

AMST-01:

Newspaper interview with peer-researcher in Amsterdam

Annex 2

SEVI-01

Stickers by Mujeres Supervivientes

Annex 3

WROC-01

Materials used in the case study
of Wrocław for the mapping and
action group consolidation

COMMUNITY SUPPORT ACADEMY

If you are a member of the migrant community, we invite you to a series of training sessions on how the system works in Poland and how to protect yourself against abuse.

- 18.09 8 p.m. - 18:00 Tenants' rights in Poland: protection against unfair landlords
- 24.09 8 p.m. - 18:00 Taxes and health insurance in Poland: a practical guide
- 02.10 8 p.m. - 18:00 Procedures for legalising residence and work in Poland: a practical guide
- 04.10 8 p.m. - 15:00 Labour law in Poland and protection against abuse by employers

The training will be conducted online in English with translation into Spanish. It is completely free of charge.

If you want to participate in the training, please send your application to tomasz.bauer@nomada.info.pl

Detailed information can be found on our website. Use the QR code.

The training project was organized as part of the "Rights for All" project, implemented by Nomada, co-funded by PICUM, and funded by the European Commission.

ACADEMIA DE APOYO A LA COMUNIDAD

Si eres miembro de la comunidad migrante, te invitamos a una serie de sesiones formativas sobre cómo funciona el sistema en Polonia y cómo protegerte contra los abusos.

- 18/09 18:00 Derechos de los inquilinos en Polonia: protección frente a arrendadores deshonestos
- 24/09 18:00 Impuestos y seguro médico en Polonia: guía práctica
- 02/10 18:00 Procedimientos para legalizar la estancia y el trabajo en Polonia: guía práctica
- 04/10 15:00 Derecho laboral en Polonia y protección contra los abusos de los empleadores

La formación se impartirá en línea en inglés con traducción al español. Es totalmente gratuita.

Si desea participar en la formación, envíe su solicitud a tomasz.bauer@nomada.info.pl

Encontrará información detallada en nuestra página web. Utilice el código QR.

El proyecto de formación se organiza en el marco del proyecto "Rights for All", financiado por PICUM, y financiado por la Comisión Europea.

ACADEMIA DE APOYO A LA COMUNIDAD

Si eres miembro de la comunidad migrante, te invitamos a una serie de sesiones formativas sobre cómo funciona el sistema en Polonia y cómo protegerte contra los abusos.

- 18/09 Derechos de los inquilinos en Polonia
18:00 Protección frente a arrendadores deshonestos
- 24/09 Impuestos y seguro médico en Polonia
18:00 Guía práctica
- 02/10 Procedimientos para legalizar la estancia
18:00 y el trabajo en Polonia: Guía práctica
- 04/10 Derecho laboral en Polonia y protección
15:00 contra los abusos de los empleadores

La formación se impartirá en línea en inglés con traducción al español. Es totalmente gratuita.

Si desea participar en la formación, envíe su solicitud a tomasz.bauer@nomada.info.pl

Encontrará información detallada en nuestra página web. Utilice el código QR.

Annex 4

WROC-02

Petition by the Latin American workers' union in Poland

OGÓLNOPOLSKI ZWIĄZEK ZAWODOWY
INICJATYWA PRACOWNICZA

Warsaw, 12 November 2025

Senator Magdalena Biejat
Senate of the Republic of Poland
ul. Wiejska 6
00-902 Warsaw

PETITION

regarding the protection of migrant workers' rights and the reform of regulations on residence and labour legalisation

Dear Senator,

On behalf of the Commission of Workers from Latin America (Sindicato de Trabajadores Latinoamericanos en Polonia) of the All-Poland Trade Union "Workers' Initiative" (Ogólnopolski Związek Zawodowy Inicjatywa Pracownicza), we appeal for a legislative initiative aimed at strengthening the protection of migrant workers in Poland and ensuring that national regulations comply with international labour standards.

1. We demand the right of residence for migrants who have brought cases against their employers to court

The current regulations treat migrant workers differently than Polish citizens. Migrants can be penalised for so-called informal work - those performing work not in compliance with existing regulations are subject to fines, and additionally, the lack of required documents may result in an order to return to their country of origin. As a result, part of the responsibility for illegal employment falls on the worker, even though the employer bears full responsibility for the legalisation of employment. This practice raises serious concerns, especially since in the case of domestic workers, the employer alone would be liable for similar violations (for example, employing someone without mandatory medical examinations). This constitutes a breach of the principle of equal treatment of workers. The current framework leads to a situation in which migrant workers are afraid to report violations of their rights for fear of receiving a return order. Consequently, migrants endure exploitation in exchange for being allowed to work, while dishonest employers benefit from cheap, unprotected labour.

2. We demand an end to the obligation of the National Labour Inspectorate (PIP) to inform the Border Guard

We demand that the National Labour Inspectorate no longer be obliged to inform the Border Guard about cases of informal employment of foreigners or to conduct joint inspections. The current obligation discourages victims of exploitation from reporting abuses and effectively turns the Inspectorate into a body of immigration control. This contradicts International Labour Organization (ILO) Convention No. 81, in force in Poland since 1995, which clearly states that labour inspectors should not perform duties that interfere with their primary function of protecting workers' rights (Article 3(2) of the Convention).

3. We demand that the National Labour Inspectorate be granted new powers

In September 2025, amendments were proposed to the Act regulating the National Labour Inspectorate, aiming to allow administrative conversion of civil law contracts into employment contracts. We demand that labour inspectors also be empowered to administratively establish employment relationships where there is no written contract. Based on our experience, employers - especially in sectors with a high proportion of migrant workers such as construction, agriculture, and logistics - frequently fail to sign contracts with employees. As a result, migrants lose the possibility of regularising their employment and residence. The National Labour Inspectorate should have the authority to counteract such situations.

4. We demand the introduction of legal provisions enabling the legalisation of residence for non-EU citizens residing irregularly in Poland

We call for the introduction of a legal framework allowing third-country nationals residing in Poland without work or residence permits to apply for a temporary residence and work permit by proving their ties to Poland. A similar system, known as “arraigo”, has been successfully implemented in Spain, encompassing five main categories: social, labour, training, family, and “second chance”. In most cases, a two-year period of residence is required. For example, “social arraigo” requires at least two years of residence and evidence of integration through family, employment, or economic links, while “second-chance arraigo” allows regularisation for those who held legal residence within the past two years but were unable to renew it.

We believe that Poland should not only enable new migrant workers to work legally but also provide an opportunity for those who already live and work here to regularise their employment and residence. At present, many migrants we represent fall into irregular status due to the actions of employers, while the existing legal mechanisms and institutional framework offer them no means to claim their rights or change their situation. Legalisation of work and residence, along with the ability to bring cases to court regarding employer abuses with the support of state institutions, would allow migrants to fully participate in the social and economic life of the country—strengthening solidarity and social stability.

Respectfully,

On behalf of the Commission of Workers from Latin America
(Sindicato de Trabajadores Latinoamericanos en Polonia)
All-Poland Trade Union “Workers’ Initiative”
(Ogólnopolski Związek Zawodowy „Inicjatywa Pracownicza”)

Rocio Flores Torres

Deliverable information

Deliverable factsheet	
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WP7 Participatory Action Research (PAR)

Migrant organisations led actions

About DignityFIRM

Towards becoming sustainable and resilient societies we must address the structural contradictions between our societies' exclusion of migrant workers and their substantive role in producing our food.

www.dignityfirm.eu

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